

THE STUDY OF TENSILE BEHAVIOUR ON C/G SANDWICH LAMINATES OF
HYBRID FIBER REINFORCED ESF/PSF

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ABSTRACT

A theory has been presented here to design the C/G sandwich hybrid laminates of different resin system. The study shows this theory is agreement with the experiment very well and also agree well with the published work.

INTRODUCTION

Though polysulfone (PSF) has many good performances, such as high strength, good dimension stability, resistant erosion and high working temperature, its process is difficult due to high glassy temperature. If 10 percent of bis (4-(4-ethynylphenoxy) phenyl) sulfone (ESF) is added into PSF, compared with the PSF, the new blend, ESF/PSF, possesses low processing temperature and melt viscosity, and its products can bear at higher working temperature after proper heat-treatment. Such a new blend will be a good matrix materials for manufacture advance structural composites, and their mechanical behaviours are concerned. So this paper investigates for the C/G hybrid sandwich laminates composed of both carbon and glass fiber hybrid reinforced ESF/PSF on tensile Behaviour theoretically and experimentally. The satisfying results of both experiment and theory have been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. SPECIMENTS

The unidirection C/G hybrid sandwich laminates component ratio is tabulated in table 1. The skins are CFRP and the cores are GFRP for all C/G sandwich laminates. The properties of components are as follows: the strengths and moduli of carbon and glass fiber are $\sigma_{cf}=2600\text{MPa}$, $\sigma_{gf}=2300\text{MPa}$; $E_{cf}=191\text{GPa}$, $E_{gf}=85.1\text{GPa}$. And properties of the blend, ESF/PSF, are $\sigma_m=46.9\text{MPa}$ and $E_m=2.48\text{GPa}$. Its tensile failure strain $\epsilon_{mf}=0.0176$ so this matrix is rather brittle.

Table 1.

Group	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Volume fraction of carbon fiber in amount fiber $V_{cf}/V_f(\%)$	0 (GFRP)	11.4	25	36.6	50	66.6	83.3	100 (CFRP)
Volume fraction of total fiber $U_f(\%)$	53	53.5	60	58	60	60	60	58

The specimens designed in the form of a strip with tabs are 170mm long, 6mm wide and 'as-received' thickness. The Aluminium tabs adhered at the strip's ends are 50mm long, 6mm wide and 1mm thickness. There are five specimens each group.

2. TEST METHOD AND RESULTS

The experiemnts have been performed on Instron 8032 with testing vilocity $V=1\text{mm/min}$. And the $\sigma - \epsilon$, stress-strain curves, are determined by a transducer directly.

From the observation during the test, all tested specimens are first split transversely on outer surface, and then delaminated along the both interface of CFRP and GFRP and fractured at last. While the ratio of V_{cf}/V_f is small, after the specimen split, it is going to sustain a certain load. However the ratio of V_{cf}/V_f becomes large, after the specimen split and delimitate, it will fast unload to fail immediately. Due to splitting, the transducer mounted on specimen outer surface is loose, the σ - ϵ curve will be invalid. So that the whole process of the experiment would not be represented by σ - ϵ curve only the ultimate stress σ_u and the modulus E_H are detected. As the last experimental results. the behaviour of tensile via component parameter, E_H-V_{cf}/V_f and σ_u-V_{cf}/V_f , are given in Fig.1 and Fig.2.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS AND THE COMPARISON WITH THE EXPERIMENTS

As shown in Fig.3 in the elastic range, the following equations could be easily written for a C/G sandwich strip:

$$\sigma_H t d = 2\sigma_c t_c d + 2\sigma_g t_g d \quad (1)$$

and

$$\sigma_H/E_H = \sigma_c/E_c = \sigma_g/E_g \quad (2)$$

Accordingly, from eqs. (1)-(2), the total modulus E_H is given:

$$E_H = E_c t_c / (t_c + t_g) + E_g t_g / (t_c + t_g) \quad (3)$$

Fig.1 E_H-V_{cf}/V_f

Fig.2 σ_u-V_{cf}/V_f and ϵ_u-V_{cf}/V_f

Fig.3 Tensile Strip

From the test observation and the previous studies²⁻⁴, it has been already clear that in the tensile test the failure of the component of having small break elongation, e.g. carbon fiber, doesn't lead to change the slope of the initial straight section of σ - ϵ curve. When whole CFRP on the surface of the specimen has been split and the interfacial bonding of both FRP become failed, in a moment, the slope of the straight section of the curve changes obviously, simultaneously, the stress reaches its ultimate value, σ_u . Moreover, the following equation exists, that is

$$\sigma_u/E_H = \sigma_{cu}/E_c \quad (4)$$

substituting Eq. (3) into Eq. (4), yield

$$\sigma_u = \sigma_{cu} [E_g + t_c (E_c - E_g) / (t_c + t_g)] / E_c \quad (5)$$

where, σ_{cu} is the tensile strength of the CFRP. Although the surfaces are broken this doesn't mean that the whole sandwich is failed. Especially, if the ratio V_{cf}/V_f is rather small, the core of sandwich, CFRP, can still support the loading to some stress σ'_u ;

$$\sigma'_u = \sigma_{gu} t_g / (t_c + t_g) = \sigma_{gu} [1 - t_c / (t_c + t_g)] \quad (6)$$

where σ_{gu} is the tensile strength of GFRP. The relative thickness ratios, t_c/t_c+t_g or t_g/t_c+t_g , appearing in Eqs. (3), (5) and (6) are corresponding to the volume ratios of the component, V_{cf}/V_f or V_{gf}/V_f .

When $\sigma_u = \sigma'_u$, it means that all component in C/G sandwich will be failure at the same time. It leads to a critical component volume ratio, $(V_{cf}/V_f)_{cr}$, at that point, the minimum strength value in $\sigma_u - V_{cf}/V_f$ curve could be obtained. This is

$$(V_{cf}/V_f)_{cr} = [1 + E_c \sigma_{cu} / (E_c \sigma_{gu} - E_g \sigma_{cu})]^{-1} \quad (7)$$

To compare with the experimental values, the results from theoretical calculations are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2. It is shown that there are good agreement between the theoretical and experimental results.

Substituting the data detected from this test, $E_c=116.3\text{GPa}$, $E_g=45.8\text{GPa}$, $\sigma_{cu}=1250\text{MPa}$ and $\sigma_{gu}=597\text{MPa}$, into Eq.(7), gives $(V_{cf}/V_f)_{cr}=8\%$, since this critical value is very small, so that the behaviour of $\sigma_u - V_{cf}/V_f$, both of theory and experiment, obeys a linear regularity approximately, but the behaviour of $E_H - V_{cf}/V_f$ is conformed to the Rule of Mixture (ROM) as shown in Figs.1 and 2.

DISCUSSION

(1) Reference 5 has presented another theory from fiber component to calculate the C/G sandwich laminates of epoxy resin. A satisfactory results were obtained too. If the theory in this paper is applied to treat the data presented in reference 5, the results will be better fit with the experiment, as shown in Fig.4.

It is interesting to point out that there would be the same calculating results for the C/G sandwich laminate both of the reference 5 and this paper if the condition which the tensile properties on testing and calculating of CFRP and GFRP conform to the Rule of Mixture. Otherwise, the bigger discrepancy would be created between those theories. But the theory suggested here has more widely usability for dealing with the C/G sandwich laminates with different resin system.

Fig.4 $\sigma_u - V_{cf}/V_f$

(2) In the lower part of Fig.2, the measured strain curve, $\epsilon_u - V_{cf}/V_f$, has been plotted too. Some important information have been revealed in it. First of all, despite the glass fiber possessing a good failure elongation, the GFRP has a low failure strain $\epsilon_{gu}=0.0133$. And in the second place, the graph can be divided into two parts from the point at $V_{cf}/V_f=25\%$. At its left, the synergistic effect of GFRP and CFRP

can be observed. Namely, due to the influenced of GFRP delaying the failure of CFRP, and the failure strains of C/G sandwich laminates have a slightly bigger value, but at its right, these sandwich structures are basically controlled by CFRP. Their failure strains are almost equal to the failure strain of CFRP, that is $\epsilon_{cu}=0.0103$. These results showed: the refined polysulfone, ESF/PSF, and its composites, especially for GFRP, on tensile in room temperature are not as good as what is expected, and all the eight-group test reveals that the nature of the material is brittle. That means their application to some engineering structures if they are going to be subjected to fatigue, fracture, impact and so on will be restricted.

CONCLUSION

The experiments here showed that in the room temperature the mechanical behaviour of C/G sandwich laminates of refined polysulfone possess the following peculiarities: the strengths conform to a linearity approximately and moduli allow the ROM against the variation of V_{cf}/V_f ; the behaviour of materials is slightly brittle.

The theory suggested here is suitable for the composites of different resin system. And it could be used as the reference on designing the sandwich laminates and studying their hybrid effect.

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